

COMPARISON OF SINGLE DOSE VERSUS MULTIPLE DOSES ANTIBIOTIC PROPHYLAXIS IN SURGICAL SITE INFECTION AT A TEACHING HOSPITAL

Dr. Hamala Khan^{*1}, Dr. Riaz Ahmed Chaudhry²

^{*1}Post Graduate Trainee (FCPS General Surgery), Divisional Headquarters Hospital, Mirpur, AJ&K

²Professor of Surgery (Study Supervisor), Divisional Headquarters Hospital, Mirpur, AJ&K

^{*1}hamala.khan94@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18334973>

Keywords

Surgical Site Infection, Antibiotic Prophylaxis, Single-Dose Regimen, Multiple-Dose Regimen, Postoperative Complications, Antimicrobial Resistance.

Article History

Received: 10 February 2025

Accepted: 26 March 2025

Published: 15 April 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Hamala Khan

Abstract

Background: Surgical site infection (SSI) is a frequent postoperative problem. Multiple-dose prophylaxis has drawbacks, while evidence supports single-dose use. However, controversy persists in literature; therefore, this study was planned to compare both regimens.

Objective: To compare single dose versus multiple doses antibiotic prophylaxis in surgical site infection at a teaching hospital.

Duration: Six months w.e.f. 23-04-2024 to 22-10-2024.

Methodology: After ethical approval, 200 elective surgery patients at DHQ Hospital Mirpur, AJ&K, were randomized into two groups: Group A received a single dose of ceftriaxone, and Group B received a multiple-dose antibiotic prophylaxis regimen. Standard protocols, uniform care, blinding, and weekly follow-ups were ensured. SSI diagnosis was consultant-confirmed, and data were coded to minimize bias.

Results: A total of 200 patients with mean age 40.21±11.97 years were included. Males predominated (68.5%), and most were overweight or ASA-II. Diabetes was present in 43%. Laparotomy, appendectomy, and hernia repair were common procedures. SSI occurred in 13% of Group A and 16% of Group B (p=0.547), with no significant differences found after stratification by age, BMI, or comorbidities (p>0.05).

Conclusion: Single-dose and multiple-dose antibiotic prophylaxis demonstrated comparable effectiveness in preventing surgical site infections. No significant differences were found overall or across subgroups stratified by age, gender, BMI, ASA status, diabetes, or surgical procedure. These results indicate that a single-dose regimen is equally effective as multiple doses for SSI prevention.

INTRODUCTION

A surgical site infection (SSI) refers to an infection that develops at the location of a surgical incision, which may involve only the superficial tissues or extend into the deeper fascial layers, within a defined postoperative period (1). SSIs are recognized as the most frequent category of healthcare-associated

infections and make up a considerable proportion of hospital-acquired infections (2). Their occurrence often results in extended hospitalization, higher chances of long-term complications, increased economic burden, and a reduction in the overall effectiveness of surgical procedures (3).

Several patient-related factors increase the risk of SSI. These include existing infections, malnutrition, obesity, hypoalbuminemia, advanced age, smoking habits, and immunosuppressive states (4). Surgical factors also play a role, such as operations performed under contaminated conditions, emergency procedures, prolonged surgeries, inadequate sterilization, improper handling of surgical instruments, and insufficient preparation of the operative site with antiseptic measures (5). In addition, certain physiological conditions predispose patients to SSIs, including multiple traumas, hemodynamic instability, shock, major intraoperative blood transfusions, and postoperative complications. Abdominal operations and procedures performed in contaminated or less sterile environments are also considered independent predictors of SSI (6).

In developing countries like Pakistan, the absence of well-structured surveillance systems makes it difficult to routinely monitor SSI rates. SSI continues to be a major healthcare challenge, and nearly every hospital faces this burden. Effective surgical outcomes depend not only on the operative procedure itself but also on the prevention and management of surgical wounds (5,6). In Abbottabad, Pakistan, a study reported frequency of SSI as high as 33.68% (7).

The use of prophylactic antibiotics has been a standard strategy for reducing SSIs. A single-dose regimen of antimicrobial prophylaxis is considered both cost-effective and clinically advantageous (8). Recent evidence reinforces this shift. Studies by Kim et al. in clean-contaminated surgeries have demonstrated that extending prophylaxis beyond the preoperative dose offers no additional protection against SSI but significantly increases hospital costs and the risk of adverse events. Furthermore, updated guidelines from the CDC and ASHP increasingly advocate for zero post-operative doses to combat the global surge in antimicrobial resistance (9).

Haider et al. in Pakistan demonstrated a significantly lower SSI rate in patients receiving a single-dose regimen compared to those given multiple doses (4.28% vs. 9.63%; $p=0.042$). This finding emphasizes the potential benefit of promoting single-dose prophylaxis to reduce cost and minimize antibiotic resistance (10). Sumukha reported higher SSI in single-dose than multiple-dose patients (8% vs. 0%,

$p>0.05$) (11). Similarly, Nusrath et al. noted lower SSI in single-dose (11.3% vs. 14.7%, $p=0.40$) (12).

The available literature shows conflicting findings, with no definitive conclusion regarding whether single-dose or multiple-dose antibiotic prophylaxis is more effective in preventing surgical site infections. Due to this uncertainty, the present study aimed to re-assess and compare the efficacy of both approaches. Reaching a clear recommendation would provide valuable guidance for clinical practice, support better surgical outcomes, reduce the burden of infection, lower treatment costs, and help minimize unnecessary antibiotic use.

METHODOLOGY

The randomized controlled trial was conducted in the Department of General Surgery, Divisional Headquarters Hospital, Mirpur, AJ&K, over a six-month period after obtaining approval of study synopsis by the ethical review committee. A total of 200 patients were enrolled, with 100 allocated to each group. The sample size was calculated using a test power of 80% and a significance level of 5%, considering an expected SSI frequency of 8% in the single-dose group compared to 0% in the multiple-dose group. Non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used. Surgical procedures included elective laparotomy, appendectomy, and incisional or inguinal hernia. Surgical Site Infection (SSI) was clinically diagnosed by a consultant surgeon within 30 days post-surgery. A diagnosis was made if at least two of the following criteria were present: localized erythema (redness) surrounding the incision, serosanguineous or purulent discharge from the wound, or a documented axillary temperature greater than 100.4°F (38°C). All diagnoses were confirmed by the attending senior consultant to maintain diagnostic consistency. Patients of both genders aged 18 to 60 years undergoing elective surgical procedures as per operational definition were included. Patients with ASA status III or IV, ischemic heart disease, existing infection, or those requiring emergency procedures were excluded. Eligible patients were counseled, informed consent was obtained, detailed data were recorded, and participants were allocated to two study groups. Group A received a single 2g dose of ceftriaxone intravenously at the induction of anesthesia. Group

B received an initial 2g dose of ceftriaxone at induction, followed by 1g intravenously twice daily for two days post-operatively. To ensure a double-blind design, Group A was administered an identical-appearing placebo (normal saline) on the same post-operative schedule as Group B. Both the active drug and the placebo were prepared in identical syringes to maintain participant blinding. All surgical procedures followed standard hospital protocols, and patients were advised to attend weekly follow-up clinics for 30 days. SSI was labelled by a senior consultant according to the defined criteria, and data were anonymized by the resident to minimize bias, with confounding variables controlled through exclusion. Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 27. Age and BMI were summarized as mean±SD, while ASA status, surgery type, and SSI were reported as frequencies and percentages. The Chi-square test assessed SSI differences between groups, with p≤0.05 considered significant. Stratified analyses were performed for age, BMI, gender, and ASA status.

RESULTS

The study included 200 patients with a mean age of 40.21±11.97 years, ranging from 18 to 60 years. Of these, 91 patients were between 18 and 40 years, while 109 were aged 41 to 60 years. The majority were male, comprising 137 patients, compared to 63 females. The mean BMI was 25.80±3.56 kg/m², with 85 (42.5%) patients falling in the normal weight category and 115 (57.5%) classified as overweight or obese. Regarding ASA status, 63 (31.5%) patients

were ASA-I, while the majority, 137 (68.5%), were ASA-II. Diabetes was present in 86 (43.0%) patients, whereas 114 (57.0%) were non-diabetic. With respect to the type of surgical procedures, laparotomy and appendectomy were performed in 70 (35.0%) cases each, while hernia repair (incisional/inguinal) was carried out in 60 (30.0%) patients, as shown in Table 1. The groups were comparable in baseline characteristics, showing no significant differences (p>0.05) (Table 2).

Table 3 shows the comparison of surgical site infections between the two groups. In Group A, 13 (13.0%) patients developed surgical site infection compared to 16 (16.0%) patients in Group B. Although the proportion of infections was slightly high in Group B, the difference was not statistically significant (p=0.547).

Table 4 shows comparison of SSI frequencies between the groups after stratification. No statistically significant differences were observed across age, gender, BMI, ASA status, diabetes, or type of surgical procedure (p>0.05). In younger patients (18–40 years), SSI was 16.3% in Group A and 18.8% in Group B, while in the 41–60 years group it was 10.5% and 13.5%, respectively. Males had similar infection rates (15.5% vs. 16.7%), whereas females showed 6.9% (2/29) in Group A and 14.7% (5/34) in Group B (p = 0.326). Infection rates also did not differ significantly when stratified by BMI, ASA status, diabetes, or surgical procedure.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Characteristics	Total (200)
Age (years)	40.21±11.97
• 18-40 years	91 (45.5%)
• 41-60 years	109 (54.5%)
Gender	
• Male	137 (68.5%)
• Female	63 (31.5%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.80±3.56
• Normal Weight	85 (42.5%)

• Overweight/Obese	115 (57.5%)
ASA Status	
• ASA-I	63 (31.5%)
• ASA-II	137 (68.5%)
Diabetes	
• Yes	86 (43.0%)
• No	114 (57.0%)
Type of Surgical Procedure	
• Laparotomy	70 (35.0%)
• Appendectomy	70 (35.0%)
• Hernia (Incision/Inguinal)	60 (30.0%)

Table 2: Comparison of Baseline Characteristics

Characteristics	Group A (n=100)	Group B (n=100)	p-value
Age (years)	40.46±11.6	39.95±12.33	0.764
• 18-40 years	43 (43.0%)	48 (48.0%)	0.478
• 41-60 years	57 (57.0%)	52 (52.0%)	
Gender			
• Male	71 (71.0%)	66 (66.0%)	0.447
• Female	29 (29.0%)	34 (34.0%)	
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.67±3.53	25.93±3.61	0.600
• Normal Weight	47 (47.0%)	38 (38.0%)	0.198
• Overweight/Obese	53 (53.0%)	62 (62.0%)	
ASA Status			
• ASA-I	33 (33.0%)	30 (30.0%)	0.648
• ASA-II	67 (67.0%)	70 (70.0%)	
Diabetes			
• Yes	41 (41.0%)	45 (45.0%)	0.568
• No	59 (59.0%)	55 (55.0%)	
Type of Surgical Procedure			
• Laparotomy	29 (29.0%)	41 (41.0%)	0.108
• Appendectomy	35 (35.0%)	35 (35.0%)	

• Hernia (Incision/Inguinal)	36 (36.0%)	24 (24.0%)	
------------------------------	------------	------------	--

Statistical significance was determined using the Chi-square/Fisher's Exact test, with a p-value threshold of ≤ 0.05

Table 3: Comparison of Study Outcomes between the Groups

Characteristics	Group A (n=100)	Group B (n=100)	p-value
Surgical Site Infection			
• Yes	13 (13.0%)	16 (16.0%)	0.547
• No	87 (87.0%)	84 (84.0%)	

Chi Square test, p-value ≤ 0.05 as significant

Table 4: Comparison of Stratification of Frequency of SSI between the Groups

Group	Sub Group	Group A (n=100)	Group B (n=100)	p-value
Age	18-40 years	7/43 (16.3%)	9/48 (18.8%)	0.757
	41-60 years	6/57 (10.5%)	7/52 (13.5%)	0.767
Gender	Male	11/71 (15.5%)	11/66 (16.7%)	0.852
	Female	2/29 (6.9%)	5/34 (14.7%)	0.326
BMI	Normal Weight	7/47 (14.9%)	8/38 (21.1%)	0.459
	Overweight/Obese	6/53 (11.3%)	8/62 (12.9%)	0.796
ASA Status	ASA-I	5/33 (15.2%)	3/30 (10.3%)	0.540
	ASA-II	8/67 (11.9%)	13/70 (18.6%)	0.282
Diabetes	Yes	6/41 (14.6%)	7/45 (15.6%)	0.905
	No	7/59 (11.9%)	9/55 (16.4%)	0.490
Type of Surgical Procedure	Laparotomy	6/29 (20.7%)	7/41 (17.1%)	0.702
	Appendectomy	4/35 (11.4%)	5/35 (14.3%)	0.721
	Hernia (Incision/Inguinal)	3/36 (8.3%)	2/24 (16.7%)	0.325

DISCUSSION

SSI is a major postoperative complication that increases patient morbidity, hospital stay, and healthcare costs (1,3). Traditionally, multiple-dose antibiotic prophylaxis has been used to reduce the risk of SSI; however, prolonged use leads to higher cost, antimicrobial resistance, and adverse drug effects (4). Evidence from recent studies suggests that a single-dose regimen may be equally effective while

avoiding these drawbacks. Despite this, controversy exists in the literature, with some studies favoring multiple doses and others supporting a single dose (10,12). Therefore, this study was planned to compare both regimens in a teaching hospital setting in patients undergoing elective surgical procedures. A comparison of our findings with previously published studies reveals both similarities and differences. Haider et al. in Pakistan observed a

notably lower rate of surgical site infections in the single-dose group compared to the multiple-dose group, supporting the use of a single-dose regimen (10). Conversely, Sumuka in India reported a higher SSI rate in the single-dose group than in the multiple-dose group, although this difference was not statistically significant (11). Similarly, Nusrath et al. in India found fewer infections in the single-dose group compared with multiple doses, but the difference lacked statistical significance (12). Kumar et al. in India studied patients undergoing elective cholecystectomy and reported comparable infection rates between single- and multiple-dose groups, concluding that a single intravenous antibiotic at induction was as effective as multiple doses (13). Yadav et al. in Nepal observed similar outcomes in laparoscopic cholecystectomy, with wound infection rates nearly identical between the two prophylaxis regimens, indicating equivalent efficacy (14). Waheed et al. in Pakistan evaluated caesarean sections and found no significant difference in postoperative wound infections between single- and multiple-dose groups (15). Gahm et al. in Sweden, in a randomized trial on implant-based breast reconstruction, demonstrated that multiple-dose prophylaxis offered no advantage over a single dose and noted that prolonged antibiotic use increased the risk of adverse effects (16). Further supporting these findings, Vala et al. in India reported similar SSI rates between single- and multiple-dose groups in caesarean sections, while Igwemadu et al. in the United Kingdom concluded that single-dose prophylaxis was equally effective in preventing infections (17,18). Durai S. et al. in India observed that infection rates in the single-dose group were comparable or lower than those in the multiple-dose group, reinforcing the potential benefit of single-dose regimens (19). Finally, Das et al. in India examined additional postoperative outcomes, including fever, tachycardia, leukocytosis, and wound discharge, and found no significant differences between single- and multiple-dose groups. They highlighted that single-dose prophylaxis is not only effective but also more cost-efficient, particularly in clean and clean-contaminated surgical procedures (20).

The stratified analysis of the study provides important insight into why single-dose prophylaxis is not inferior, even among high-risk groups such as

patients with diabetes and obesity. Single-dose prophylaxis proved effective in patients with diabetes mellitus, showing efficacy comparable to multiple-dose regimens. This suggests that infection risk in diabetics is primarily determined by host-related metabolic and immune dysfunction rather than the duration of antibiotic use. In the present analysis, 43% of patients were diabetic, yet no significant difference in SSI rates was observed between the single-dose and multiple-dose groups (14.6% vs. 15.6%, $p = 0.905$). This finding aligns with established physiological mechanisms, as hyperglycemia-induced neutrophil dysfunction, impaired chemotaxis, and defective bacterial opsonization are the main contributors to increased infection susceptibility in diabetic patients, rather than insufficient antibiotic coverage. Prolonging antibiotic use fails to correct these cellular immune defects. Therefore, strict perioperative glycemic control, rather than extended antibiotic courses, should be prioritized for SSI prevention in diabetic patients.

Similarly, single-dose prophylaxis was not less effective than multiple-dose regimens among overweight and obese patients, indicating that SSI risk in this group is more closely related to tissue characteristics and the adequacy of the initial antibiotic dose than to the duration of exposure. Comparable outcomes were observed in overweight and obese patients receiving either single- or multiple-dose prophylaxis. Obesity is a recognized risk factor for SSI due to poor perfusion of adipose tissue and the formation of dead space. However, recent pharmacokinetic evidence suggests that prophylaxis failure in obese patients is largely attributable to under-dosing, such as failure to administer weight-adjusted doses (e.g., 3 g of cefazolin for patients over 120 kg), rather than inadequate duration of antibiotic therapy. These findings support the conclusion that single-dose prophylaxis is not inferior to multiple-dose regimens in high-BMI patients, provided that an adequate preoperative dose is administered to achieve effective tissue concentrations at the critical time of surgery.

Across different age groups and ASA classes, single-dose prophylaxis demonstrated outcomes comparable to extended regimens, reinforcing the observation that increasing antibiotic coverage does

not offset frailty-related or systemic infection risks. The study found no significant difference in efficacy based on age or ASA status. Although immunosenescence is traditionally associated with advanced age, the data demonstrate that single-dose prophylaxis effectively covers the decisive period of bacterial inoculation at the time of surgical incision. The lack of superiority in the multiple-dose group further confirms that systemic comorbidities reflected by higher ASA scores cannot be mitigated simply by extending postoperative antibiotic use and instead require comprehensive medical optimization. The majority of published studies are consistent with our findings, demonstrating that single-dose antibiotic prophylaxis is as effective as multiple-dose regimens in preventing SSIs. Although some studies report minor variations in infection rates, these differences are generally not statistically significant. In contrast, multiple-dose regimens are associated with increased risks of antibiotic resistance, adverse drug events, and additional healthcare costs without clear clinical benefit. Therefore, single-dose prophylaxis, particularly in elective clean and clean-contaminated surgeries, appears to be a safe, effective, and resource-efficient strategy.

CONCLUSION

Single-dose and multiple-dose antibiotic prophylaxis demonstrated comparable effectiveness in preventing surgical site infections. No significant differences were found overall or across subgroups stratified by age, gender, BMI, ASA status, diabetes, or surgical procedure. These results indicate that a single-dose regimen is equally effective as multiple doses for SSI prevention.

LIMITATIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

The strength of this study was its direct comparison of single- versus multiple-dose antibiotic prophylaxis in a real-world teaching hospital setting, reflecting practical surgical outcomes. Limitations included a single-center design, modest sample size, and exclusion of emergency procedures, which may affect generalizability. Future research should focus on multicenter randomized trials with larger cohorts, diverse surgical populations, and cost-effectiveness analyses to establish standardized guidelines for

antibiotic prophylaxis in preventing surgical site infections.

Conflict of Interest: None

Source of Funding: None

REFERENCES

- Ansari S, Hassan M, Barry HD, Bhatti TA, Hussain SZ, Jabeen S, et al. Risk factors associated with surgical site infections: a retrospective report from a developing country. *Cureus*. 2019;11(6):e4801.
- Hassan RS, Osman SO, Aabdeen MA, Mohamed WE, Hassan RS, Mohamed SO. Incidence and root causes of surgical site infections after gastrointestinal surgery at a public teaching hospital in Sudan. *Patient Saf Surg*. 2020;14(1):1-7.
- Alverdy JC, Hyman N, Gilbert J. Re-examining causes of surgical site infections following elective surgery in the era of asepsis. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2020;20(3):e38-43.
- Borle FR. Determinants of superficial surgical site infections in abdominal surgeries at a rural teaching hospital in Central India: a prospective study. *J Fam Med Prim Care*. 2019;8(7):2258.
- Khan FU, Khan Z, Fang Y. Need of guidelines and antimicrobial stewardship in Pakistan for perioperative surgical practices to prevent surgical site infections. *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak*. 2020;30(8):882-4.
- Albishi W, Albeshri MA, Mortada HH, Alzahrani K, Alharbi R, Aljuhani F, et al. Awareness and level of knowledge about surgical site infections and risks of wound infection among medical physicians in King Abdulaziz university hospital: cross-sectional study. *Interact J Med Res*. 2019;8(1):e12769.
- Sattar F, Sattar Z, Zaman M, Akbar S. Frequency of post-operative surgical site infections in a tertiary care hospital in Abbottabad, Pakistan. *Cureus*. 2019;11(3):e4243.
- Yadav UK, Raya A, Bhatta PN, Rai BK, Yadav AP, Shahi SK. Comparison between single dose versus multiple doses antibiotics in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Med Phoenix*. 2022;6(2):40-4.

- Kim HJ, et al. Efficacy of single-dose versus multiple-dose prophylactic antibiotics in colorectal surgery. *Ann Surg Treat Res*. 2024.
- Haider R, Masud M, Hasnain MR, Khan MT, Wyne A, Ehsan A, et al. Post-operative infection rate between single dose versus multiple dose antibiotic therapy in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Pak Armed Forces Med J*. 2022;72(4):1224-27.
- Sumukha SR. Efficacy of single dose versus multiple dose antibiotic prophylaxis in anterior abdominal wall hernia repair at a tertiary hospital. *Int J Surg*. 2020;4(3):230-2.
- Nusrath S, Nair A, Dasu S, Subramanyeshwar Rao T, Raju KV, Rayani BK, et al. Single-dose prophylactic antibiotic versus extended usage for four days in clean-contaminated oncological surgeries: a randomized clinical trial. *Ind J Surg Oncol*. 2020;11:378-86.
- Kumar S, Ranjan SK. A study to evaluate the efficacy of single dose versus multiple dose of pre-operative antibiotic. *Acad J Surg*. 2019;2(2):30-3.
- Yadav UK, Raya A, Bhatta P, Rai BK, Yadav AP, Shahi S. Role of single dose versus multiple doses antibiotics in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *J Nat Med Coll*. 2022;6(2):40-3.
- Waheed K, Bushra N, Rashid T, Abbas A. Comparison of single vs multiple doses of antibiotic prophylaxis in reduction post-caesarean section infection morbidity. *J Nat Med Coll*. 2023;5(1):40-3.
- Gahm J, Konstantinidou AL, Lagergren J, Sandelin K, Glimåker M, Johansson H, et al. Effectiveness of single vs multiple doses of prophylactic intravenous antibiotics in implant-based breast reconstruction: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2022;5(9):e2231438.
- Vala H, Vaja MA, Gohil AB. A comparative study of surgical site infection after single dose of preoperative antimicrobial prophylaxis versus multiple doses of antimicrobials in clean and clean contaminated abdominal surgeries. *Int Surg J*. 2020;7(4):1143-1147.
- Igwemadu GT, Eleje GU, Eno EE, et al. Single-dose versus multiple-dose antibiotics prophylaxis for preventing caesarean section postpartum infections: A randomized controlled trial. *Women's Health (Lond)*. 2022;18:17455057221101071.
- Durai S, et al. Multiple Doses Different from Single Dose in Antibiotic Prophylaxis in Voluntary Caesarean Fragment. *J Res Med Dent Sci*. 2022;10(3):14-19.
- Das S, Kundu R, Chattopadhyay BP. Comparison of single dose versus multiple doses of antibiotic prophylaxis for prevention of surgical site infection. *Int Surg J*. 2022;9(1):129-132. doi:10.18203/2349-2902.isj20215144.

